

Original article

Interplay of Glucose-6-Phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency, sickle cell anaemia, and malaria: a haematological perspective of the triad of hyper haemolysis

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Abstract

Background: Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) deficiency and Sickle cell anaemia (SCA) are both inherited red cell disorders associated with chronic haemolysis that have a similar pattern of occurrence in areas that are endemic for malaria, including Nigeria. There are various reports regarding the prevalence and relationship of G6PD deficiency, SCA, and malaria. This study aims to determine the interplay between G6PD deficiency, SCA, and malaria. **Materials and Methods:** This was a case-control study conducted over 13 months involving 235 SCA patients and 235 voluntary Hb AA controls. The clinical details and socio-demographic parameters were captured using a Case Record Form (CRF). About 5mls of blood was collected via venipuncture from each patient and used to run the G6PD enzyme assay and malaria test. Quantitative G6PD enzyme activity was assayed using a spectrophotometric method, and a malaria test was done using a rapid diagnostic test (RDT) using Parachek pf. Data was analysed using IBM SPSS version 23. **Results:** Our study did not show any difference in the prevalence of G6PD deficiency between SCA patients and Hb AA controls ($p=0.327$). There was also no significant correlation of G6PD activity and malarial RDT positivity in both SCA patients and HbA A controls (p values =0.784 and 0.414, respectively). **Conclusion:** The results obtained imply that there is indeed no association between G6PD deficiency and sickle cell anaemia. Similarly, no association was found between SCA patients with concomitant G6PD deficiency and malaria. There is therefore a need to do prospective studies to further clarify this observation and further determine the relationship between these 2 inherited haemolytic disorders and malaria.

Keywords: Glucose-6-phosphate, Haemolysis, Homozygote, Maiduguri, Malaria, Sickle cell.

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Introduction

Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) deficiency, Sickle cell disease (SCD), and Malaria represent a complex triad of haematological conditions that have co-evolved and interacted in unique ways, particularly in Malaria-endemic regions.¹ Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase is the rate-limiting step enzyme of the pentose-phosphate pathway (PPP), which reduces nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADP) to nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate hydrogen (NADPH). Deficiency of the enzyme resulting in decreased activity of the enzyme is an X-linked disorder and is the most common enzymopathy worldwide, affecting about 400 million individuals.² The defence of cells against oxidative stress becomes defective,

and affected individuals may manifest as haemolytic anaemia in response to infection like malaria, exposure to certain chemicals, and medications that include some antimalarials like primaquine³

Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency confers partial protection against severe *Plasmodium falciparum* Malaria but also predisposes individuals to haemolytic crises.² Similarly, Sick cell trait (HBAs), a carrier state of SCD, has been shown to reduce Malaria-related morbidity and mortality, illustrating the concept of balanced polymorphism.⁴ The commonest and most severe form of SCD is sickle cell anaemia (SCA), in which the sickle beta-globin gene is inherited in a homozygous state in the Mendelian autosomal recessive fashion of hereditary disease.⁵ Individuals with SCA have variability in the severity of the anaemia and degree of haemolysis at steady state. Factors like co-inheritance with α -thalassaemia and high fetal haemoglobin (HbF) percentage are associated with higher haemoglobin level and manifest with lesser haemolysis compared with those that do not have such associated factors.⁶ The interplay between G6PD deficiency and SCA presents significant clinical and haematological challenges, including altered disease susceptibility, variable treatment responses, and complications such as haemolysis, especially upon exposure to antimalarial drugs like Primaquine⁷

The public health burden of both SCA and G6PD deficiency is significant.^{8,9} Several studies have exploited the phenotypic relationship between G6PD deficiency and sickle cell anaemia with varying conclusions.¹⁰⁻¹⁶ Ahmed *et al.*,¹⁰ and Piomelli *et al.*,¹¹ have found some beneficial effect of the association, Fasola *et al.*,¹ and Antwi-Baffour *et al.*,¹² have shown a negative correlation, while Memon *et al.*,¹³ found no effect of the association. Even though they have different modes of inheritance, both disorders have a common effect of resulting in RBC haemolysis.¹⁴ It is important to determine the effect of the relationship so as to individualise management of such patients because G6PD-associated haemolysis is usually triggered by exposure to some medications and infections like malaria, the latter of which is also associated with haemolysis in SCA. We did not find any study on Medline that compared malaria RDT positivity in individuals with co-inheritance of G6PD deficiency and SCA. In addition, there is a paucity of information regarding the relationship between the two disorders in our environment,

which happens to be in the malaria endemic zone.

This paper, therefore, explores the haematological interactions among G6PD deficiency, SCA, and Malaria, shedding light on their pathophysiological mechanisms, epidemiological synergy, and implications for disease management in affected populations. By integrating current research, we aim to elucidate how these conditions collectively influence red blood cell biology, host immunity, and disease outcomes.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

The study was a hospital-based case-control study that was conducted over 13 13-month period between October 2020 and November 2021 at the Haematology unit of the Pathology department of the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital.

Study Participants

The study participants were individuals 18 years and above with SCA in steady state. Patients with Hb SS confirmed by Hb electrophoresis using Cellulose Acetate Agar in steady state, as defined by Akinola *et al.*,¹⁷ as the period free of crisis extending from at least three weeks since the last clinical event and three months or more since the previous blood transfusion to at least one week before the start of a new clinical event. Healthy adult volunteers who were aware of their Hb AA status were enrolled as controls.

Study Procedure

Quantitative G6PD assay

In the reagent kit, glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase in the RBCs is released after lysis with digitonin. The G6PD released catalyses the oxidation of G-6-P in the pentose phosphate pathway with the reduction of NADP⁺ to NADPH.¹⁸ The reduction rate of NADP⁺ to NADPH is measured as an increase in absorbance at 340nm proportional to the G6PD activity in the sample.¹⁹ Based on this principle, all patients were screened for G6PD deficiency by the Spectrophotometric quantitative assay as recommended by W.H.O.²⁰ Using commercial test reagent kit, cat No PD410, manufactured by Randox Laboratories, U.K.¹⁹ The tests were executed by addition of two and a half millilitres of blood into Ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA) bottle, a volume of 0.2mls of blood was washed with two mls aliquots of normal saline and centrifuged after each wash for 10 minutes at around 2000rpm. The procedure was repeated three times, and a red cell suspension in 0.5 mL of the solution was made. The suspension was allowed to stand for 15 minutes in a refrigerator at

40 °C and then centrifuged again. The supernatant was assayed within two hours.

At the start of the procedure, the spectrophotometer was set at a wavelength of 340nm with a temperature of 37^oC, and the light path of the cuvette was set at one cm. Next, double-distilled water was used as a blank, and its absorbance was measured and recorded; subsequently, the absorbance of the test samples was measured as follows:

A test tube was set on a rack, and one mL of triethanolamine buffer EDTA solution was added to the tube, followed by 0.03 mL of NADP solution and 0.015 mL of the prepared haemolysate. The test tube content was mixed and then incubated at 37^oC for five minutes, after which 0.015 mL of substrate solution was added and mixed gently, ready to read the absorbance. For the reading, the test tube content was emptied into a cuvette placed in the spectrophotometer, and the initial absorbance was read at zero minutes, while starting a timer simultaneously, followed by further readings of the absorbance at 1, 2, and 3 minutes. Finally, the change in absorbance per minute (-A340nm/min) was calculated by using absorbance at three minutes minus initial absorbance divided by 3.²¹

Calculation of G6PD activity: The following formula was used to calculate the G6PD activity:²¹

$$\text{mU/ erythrocytes per ml blood} = 33650 \times -A340\text{nm/min.}$$

The G6PD activity was then converted to mU/g haemoglobin using the equation.

$$\text{G6PD mU/gHb} = \text{mU} \times \text{Erythrocytes per ml} \times 100\text{Hb (g/dl)}$$

Normal Reference range; 6.97 - 20.5 U/g Hb.²¹

Rapid diagnostic test for malaria parasite

Rapid diagnostic test for malaria parasite employs immunochromatographic methods, such that as test samples flow through the membrane assembly of the device after addition of the clearance buffer, the coloured monoclonal anti-Plasmodium falciparum histidine-rich protein 2 (HRP 2) colloidal gold conjugate anti-sera form complex with the Plasmodium falciparum HRP 2 in the lysed sample. This complex moves further on the test membrane to the region where it is immobilized by the monoclonal anti-Plasmodium falciparum HRP 2 anti-sera coated on the membrane, leading to the formation of a pink-purple coloured band, which confirms a positive result. The unreacted conjugate and unbound complex move further on the membrane and are subsequently immobilised by anti-rabbit antibodies coated on

the membrane at the control region, forming a pink-purple band.²² Based on this principle, all patients were tested for the malaria parasite.

Test procedure

The Paracheck Pf kit components were brought to room temperature for 30 minutes before testing. The pouch was opened to retrieve the device, sample applicator, and desiccant. The colour of the desiccant was checked, which should be blue. The device was discarded if the desiccant had turned pink or colourless; otherwise, it was used immediately. The device was labelled with the sample identity. The vial cap of the clearing buffer provided with the kit was tightened in the clockwise direction to pierce the dropper bottle nozzle. The EDTA anticoagulated blood sample was mixed by gentle swirling, and then the sample applicator was dipped into it. The loop was ensured to be full before blotting it into the device's sample port. Two drops of the clearing buffer were immediately dropped into the buffer port.²² It was then allowed to stay for 20 minutes, and the result was read as follows.

Negative - when only one line "C" appeared in the result window.

Positive - when two lines "C" and "T" appear in the results window.

Invalid - when no "C" line appeared for either positive or negative test, that test was discarded and repeated with a new device.²²

Statistical Methods

Data obtained were analysed using the International Business Machine Statistical Package for Social Sciences (IBM SPSS Statistics version 23.0 software), SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA. The socio-demographic parameters, G6PD enzyme activity, and malaria rapid diagnostic test were summarised and presented using frequency, percentages, and tables as appropriate. The ages were presented in either mean ± SD when normality is not violated or median (Interquartile range) when normality is violated. Statistical significance was set at p < 0.05.

Ethical consideration

Ethical approval was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (UMTH/REC/22/618). Participants were counselled individually, after which informed consent was obtained from them.

Results

Socio-demographic profile of participants

The study population consisted of 470 participants, 235 of whom were SCA and the other 235 were

HbAA controls. The study participants' age (years) ranged from 18-52. The median age in years (interquartile range) among SCA patients was 22.00 (8.0), while the control group was 25.00 (10.0). There were 128 (54.5%) females and 107 (45.4%) males in the patient group, while the controls consisted of 82 (34.9%) females and 153 (65.1%) males. The majority of the participants were single, with 206 (87.7%) for the patients' group and 149 (63.4%) for controls. The remainder were either married (26 (11.1%) of patients and 84 (35.7%) of controls) or divorced (3 (1.3%) of patients and 2 (0.9%) of controls). More than half of the participants were educated; 128 (54.5%) of the patient group and 182 (77.4%) of controls had a tertiary level of education (Table 1). The participants were mostly students (167 (71.1%) SCA and 130 (55.3%) controls).

Table 1: Socio-demographic profile of participants

	SCA, n = 235	Control, n = 235
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
Sex		
Male	107(45.5)	153(65.1)
Female	128(54.5)	82(34.9)
Marital status		
Married	26(11.1)	84(35.7)
Single	206(87.7)	149(63.4)
Divorced	3(1.3)	2(0.9)
Educational level		
None	11(4.7)	6(2.6)
Primary	14(6.0)	6(2.6)
Secondary	82(34.9)	41(17.4)
Tertiary	128(54.5)	182(77.4)

There was no statistical difference in the prevalence of G6PD deficiency between patients and controls (p=0.327). Table 2

Table 2: Comparison of G6PD deficiency in SCA and controls

G6PD Deficient	t	P-value*
SCA	69(54.8)	
Control	57(45.2)	0.327

*Binomial test, t= test proportion

G6PD deficiency, Sickle cell anaemia, and Malarial parasitaemia

Malarial RDT positivity was (n=17; 7.2%) in patients and (n=19; 8.1%) in controls (Figure 1).

Sickle cell anaemia patients with G6PD deficiency (n=4; 5.8%) were malarial RDT positive compared to those with normal G6PD enzyme activity (n=13; 7.8%) (p=0.784). Similarly, controls with G6PD deficiency (n=6; 10.5%) were malaria RDT positive compared to those with normal G6PD enzyme activity (n=13; 7.3%) (P-value=0.414). Sickle cell anaemia patients with G6PD deficiency are less likely to have malaria infection compared to those without G6PD deficiency; they are similarly also less likely to have malaria infection compared to controls with G6PD deficiency. This is, however, not statistically significant (Table III).

Figure 1: Prevalence of malarial RDT positivity in SCA and controls

Table 3: Comparison of malarial RDT in SCA and control with G6PD deficiency & normal G6PD enzyme activity

G6PD	RDT Malaria			P-value ^a
	Positive	Negative	Total	
SCA				
With deficiency	4(5.8)	65(94.2)	69(100)	0.784
Without deficiency	13(7.8)	153(92.2)	166(100)	
Total	17(7.2)	218(92.8)	335(100)	
Control				
With deficiency	6(10.5)	51(89.5)	57(100)	0.414
Without deficiency	13(7.3)	165(92.7)	178(100)	
Total	19(8.1)	216(91.9)	235(100)	

^aFisher's Exact Test

Discussion

Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase enzyme activity varies among individuals in a population; low enzyme activity or a deficient state of the enzyme is associated with episodes of haemolysis following exposure to infection or some drugs, such as antimalarials, which is also a feature of SCA, a monogenic disorder that affects red blood cells. The coinheritance of G6PD deficiency and SCA can lead to a more complex interplay with malaria. Over the years, reported studies have shown that there is a variation in the prevalence of G6PD deficiency in sickle cell anaemic patients.¹⁰⁻¹⁶ While some studies suggest the incidence of G6PD deficiency to be higher in patients with SCA than in the general population without the haemoglobinopathy,^{23,24} our study did not find G6PD deficiency to be higher in SCA patients compared to HbAA controls. This is similar to the reports by Samuel *et al.*,²⁵ Bouanga *et al.*,²⁶ and Simpore *et al.*,²⁷ believing rather that the mutated genes responsible for both the G6PD and the SCA do not stay on the same chromosome, so they cannot be linked together.^{26,27} Therefore, a difference in the frequency of G6PD deficiency among SCA patients can only occur by postzygotic selection, indeed by postnatal selection, since the phenotypic expression of the homozygous S condition is not clinically significant until at least a few months after birth.²⁸ Diop *et al.*,²⁹ however, found G6PD deficiency to be higher in SCA patients compared to the general population without the disorder. This can probably be explained by the difference in study participants, the method of estimation of G6PD, and the geographic location of the study. Bienzle *et al.*²⁸ and Okafor *et al.*³⁰, on the other hand, found a lower prevalence of G6PD deficiency in SCA patients compared to patients without the disorder. The differences in prevalence could be due to patient selection; Bienzle *et al.* included only male Paediatric patients, whereas our study was conducted in adult patients of both genders.

Our report also shows that SCA patients with concurrent G6PD enzyme deficiency have a similar prevalence of malaria positivity compared to those with HbAA. This is similar to what was reported by a study by Okafor *et al.*³⁰ Despite the well-reported protection of G6PD deficiency and HbS against malaria,³¹ coinheritance of the two disorders did not relate to lower malarial infection rate. This finding may be limited to the fact that a more sensitive testing for malarial parasitaemia was not used, and protection may probably be with regard to severe acute infection, but not simple malarial

infection.³⁰ There were reports from early field studies that *Plasmodium falciparum* and *Plasmodium vivax* malaria parasites preferentially invade immature red blood cells that have relatively higher G6PD enzyme activity^{32,33}

Conclusion

There is no association between G6PD deficiency and sickle cell anaemia in our study. Patients with co-existing G6PD deficiency and SCA have a similar prevalence of malaria infection compared to SCA patients with normal G6PD enzyme activity.

Limitation

This study is limited by the fact that the assessment of G6PD enzyme activity was not done by a molecular study, which is more accurate and specific. Moreover, patients with acquired deficiency because of increased oxidative stress may be wrongly classified as G6PD deficient and thus may overestimate the burden of the disease.

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Competing Interest

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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